

Typical And Non-Typical Reproductive Birds of Guba and Altiaghaj Forests

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It was acknowledged that Eastern Caucasus forests are different zoogeographical regions unlike Talish forests. There is more or less information about the avifauna of the region from XIX century up to now, but comparative information on the level of use of forests by birds is the first initiative. Material given in the article is the original one; it has been collected by the author in 2013-2015, and it is in a population level. Multiparameter assessment was made for the material.

Keywords: birds, fauna, number dynamics, species, areal

The main reason creating the modern mosaic feature of the territory is related to the impacts of anthropic and anthropogenic origin. At present, birds can be divided into two groups according to the level of use of forest: Typical forest birds and non-typical forest birds. All the life of the first group is related to the forests, the second group brood at forests, but they fly to other open areas and bushes for food and other necessities.

Typical forest birds – Birds that are typical for forests lay their eggs in the nest on the trees, hide in the tree and protect itself and its generation; they are fed, rest and sleep in the tree. Classical example for typical forest birds is woodpecker – Picidae. Azerbaijani people call woodpecker as “the professional doctor” of the forest. They brood in the hole of old tree. If it doesn't like the hole which it finds, in this case, it repairs the hole or makes nest for itself by broaching rotten body of an old tree. Diameter of access road to the nest varies depending on the size of its owner.

Feathers of woodpecker standing as stiff as bow and two of its fingers turning forward and two of them backward ensures its vertical stand on the trunk of the tree. Its strong beak, tip of which is swollen, like chisel, its skull consisting of tough and big bones specializes for striking strong hits. Its tongue is long and sticky like glue, its root is united with the front part of the mouth; it comes out from its mouth, sticks insect and then it is pulled back. Hunting insects in this way doesn't require too much power.

Woodpecker doesn't like to go out of forest. In the open area, you can see woodpecker only flying from one forest to another. And its flying is undulating and weak. Its alighting on the ground can be observed only in one case when eating insects. We couldn't see woodpecker except *Picus viridis* and *Dendrocopus*.

Certhia familiaris and *Sitta europea* are a bit like to woodpecker according to the level of use of

forests in the area researched by us. Woodpecker searches for the insects of trunk by climbing from bottom to top, but *Sitta europea* looks for it by going down from top. Bark of the tree is peeled off from the lower tip, while being in suspended condition on the top, *Picidae* finds the hidden insect in the edge, and *Sitta europea* eats the insect under the bark adjacent with its bottom tip which is broken from top. *Certhia familiaris* eats the insect hiding in the narrowest cracks of dry hull with the help of thin and curved beak like arc. However, none of them can make nest for themselves by broaching the trunk. Forest bird, such as *Sitta europea* was observed while eating coagulated blood around the nearby slaughter house.

Non-typical forest birds – Non-typical forest birds make nests in the forest, bush or directly on the ground; hide themselves and their generation, rest and sleep. However, in a thick forest, umbrella of trees covers everywhere like a green tent, and nothing is seen in the forest while looking from top. Therefore, birds looking for food on the ground are to fly to open areas around them, and they quickly fly down when they their catching on the ground. Many birds live in the forests, but they make nests on the ground or bushes, brood, are fed, and don't alight on tall trees. There are birds doing the opposite of it, such birds make nests on the trees, brood, and they are to alight to other places for food. Let's review the facts.

Ciconia ciconia live in foothill zone in some places (Ismayilli), plain forests in East Caucasus (Gambarov, 1954), it has never been in Guba and Altiaghaj massif that we study (Mustafayev, 1981; Sadigova, 2010), *Ciconia nigra* has not been noted in Altiaghaj forests, it has brood in Khachmaz – Yalama forests (Khanmammadov and Mustafayev, 1965), but now, it is not observed. It is sensitive to the impacts of anthropic and anthropogenic origin. *Pernis apivoris* has not been in Guba forests (Khanmammadov and Mustafayev, 1965), but it

has been in Altiaghaj forests, now, it doesn't brood. *Milvus migrans* is an ordinary bird in foothill forests of Eastern Caucasus (Khanmammadov and Mustafayev, 1965), in 1960s, it hunted mice and locusts at the back part of 200-300 hawks harvesters in the areas where grain was harvested. (Mustafayev 1985; Sadigova, 2010). Now, it is considered a rare bird. *Accipiter gentilis* sedentary lives in the mountain forests in the upper zone, (Gambarov, 1954; Mustafayev, 1985) but we didn't see it in reproduction period in Guba-Altiaghaj forests where we conducted study. However, there has been and there is *Accipiter nisus* now. *Buteo buteo* has brood in the area studied by us (Gambarov, 1954), now it is a migrant. *Hieraetus pennatus* and *Aguila pomarina* is ordinary reproductive bird, now it gives rare brood. *Aquila chrysaetos* gives brood in upper zone of mountain forests, but we couldn't see it in reproduction period in Guba and Altiaghaj massifs. *Nepohron percnoetericus* gives rare brood in steep rocks. *Aegyptius monachus* and *Cyps fulvus* is ordinary sedentary bird, but now it is rare. *Falco tinnunculus* is ordinary reproductive bird, now it is rare. *Alectoris chunar* has been in Altiaghaj massif, and now it also exists there (it is sedentary), in Guba massif, it is rare. *Perdix perdix* has passed from Shamakhi plateau to Altiaghaj mountains (Oral information of Mustafayev), but we couldn't see it in Guba massif. *Coturnix coturnix* is not less in meadows of Guba mountains, quail is less in Altiaghaj massif as the arid landscape is dominated there. *Phasianus colchianus* has been for 20-30 years in the area where we conducted study (Gambarov, 1954), but now it doesn't exist there.

We have noted 3 species belonging to *Columbidae* family in the area where we conducted studies: *Columba livia*, *Streptopelia decaocta*, *S.turtur* (the latter one comes for brooding; the previous two species are represented by the sedentary population). *Cuculus canorus* comes for brooding; it is more in Altiaghaj massifs than in Guba massifs, because there are many bushes in the place of broken forests. 6 species include in Azerbaijan's fauna from *Strigidae* family: (Mustafayev and Sadigova 2009). *Otus scopus* comes for brooding, remaining ones are sedentary. *Bubo bubo* gives rare brood in Guba forests, we haven't seen it in Altiaghaj massif, it likes dark forests. *Athene noctua* enters forest zone with the help of seliteb habitat. It broods in covered areas of destroyed roofs. We couldn't identify other remaining species of the family. *Upupa epopus* mainly broods in seliteb landscape. Usually, it finds food by immersing its beak into the ground (insects and other invertebrates). As Altiaghaj forests have been cut and there stays bushes instead of them, it

involves the birds belonging to the family of *Passeri formes*. In the area where we conducted studies, 3 species of *Hirundinidae* family are widespread (*Ptyonoprogne rupestris*, *Hirundo rustica*, *Delichon urbica*). *Calerida cristata*, *Zullula arborea*, *Alauda arvensis* belonging to *Alaudidae* family like open places.

We can note 4 species belonging to *Motacillidae* family: *Antus campestris*, *A.trivialis*, *Motacilla cinerea*, *Zanius collurio* from *Malbazamidae* family gives brood in sparse bushes. *Oriolis oridus* gives brood in the edges of the forests and thin forks of tall trees in fruit orchards by making cup-shaped nests. *Stuznis vulgaris* gives brood in the holes of old trees remaining in seliteb habitat and covered parts of buildings. We have accurately identified brooding of 3 species from *Corvidae* family: *Garrulus glandarius*, *Pica pica*, *Corvus cornix*. The reason for the latter two species passing from Samur plain and Shamakhi plateau to Guba and Altiaghaj forest zone is accepted as forest cutting and formation of anthropogenic habitats. *Troglodytes troglodytes* and *Prunella modularis* are widespread in forest zone that we studied and they live sedentary. 8 breeds, 26 species include in Azerbaijan fauna from *Sylvidae* family (Mustafayev and Sadigova, 2005). We have noted 7 species of them in the area where we conducted studies: *S.communis*, *S.atricapilla*, *Sh.mystacea*, *Fhyloscopus collibita*, *Fh.nitidus*. All of them come for reproduction. They make nests on bushes, brood and move in autumn. Though *Regulus regulus* is entomophage, it lives sedentary in mountain forests, and in winter eats insects finding them from trees. *Ficedula allicolis*, *F.parva* and *Muscicapa striata* from *Muscicapidae* family come for brooding, they brood in the holes of trees, even in semi-covered condition under the bark which is nearly broken. They can hunt insects in the air. Birds from *Turdidae* are widespread in forests and bushes. *Saxicola rubetra* and *S.torguata* brood making nest between tall grasses in mountain forest glades and edges, they move and leave in autumn. *Phoenicurus ochruros* brood by making nests in covered empty places of buildings and rocky clefts in mountains. Formation of seliteb habitats in place of forests ensures movement of this bird from mountains to valleys.

Erithacus rubecula usually broods by making nests in the hole of trees in places where there is rare trees and bushes. They are sedentary birds. *Turdus merula* lives sedentary by intensively accommodating each place where there are trees and the thickness of population is high. *Parus ateg*, *P.caeruleus* and *P.major*, belonging to *Poridar* family, live sedentary brooding in the hole of trees in mountain forests and fruit orchards. *Parus major*

has more success. *Sitta europaea* lives sedentary in forest and *S.neumayer* lives on rocks. Two of them use natural hole, *S.neumayer* makes nest itself from wet soil. *Passer domesticus* from *Passeridae* family is complete sinanthropus, seliteb habitat is widespread in forest and mountain zone. *Passer montanus* is spread by means of fruit orchards and seliteb habitats in forest and mountain zones. They brood in covered condition by making nests, *Tringillia coeleba* and *Chloris chloris* belonging to *Tringilliade* family live in everywhere where there are trees.

Spinus spinus and *Carduelis carduelis* live as the previous two species. *Acantis cannabina* likes the places where there are trees and bushes thinly, and lives sedentary. *Carpodacus erythrinus* comes for brooding making nests in bushes in valleys on the edges of mountain forests. *Coccothraustes cocconthraustes* likes the places where there are sparse trees and bushes and lives sedentary. We have noted four species belonging to *Emberizidae* family: *Emberiza calandra* and *E. sedentary*, *E.hortulana* and *E.melanocephala* are birds that come for brooding. All of them like open places where there are sparse bushes and tall grasses; sometimes they make lower nests on the ground.

1. There have been 78 reproductive birds (46 sedentary, 32 species coming for brooding) in Guba and Altiaghaj mountain forest zone of Eastern Caucasus zoographical region in 2013-2015.

2. Many birds have been deprived of reproduction in the last 30-40 years in the study area (*Ciconia nigra*, *Milvus migrans*, *Pernis apivorus*, *Buteo bateo* etc.). 2 species are completely disappeared. (*Phasianus colchicus*, *Perdix perdix*)

3. Birds can be divided into two groups according to the level of use of the area: Typical forest birds and non-typical forest birds. First group includes *Picidae* species. They can spend all their lives here without leaving forests and alighting on the ground.

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Quba Və Altiğac Meşələrində Səciyyəvi Və Qeyri-Səciyyəvi Quşların Reproduktiv Populyasiyaları

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Şərqi-Qafqaz meşələri ayrı zoocoğrafi rayon olub, buranın aviafaunasına dair məlumatlar XIX-cü əsrdən indiyə qədər olan vaxtı əhatə edir. Lakin ərazidə quşların məskunluğu populyasiya səviyyəsində müqayisə edilməyib. Məqalədə verilən məlumatlar müəllif tərəfindən 2013-2015-ci illərdə toplanıb. Materialın ekoloji qiymətləndirilməsi multiparametrlili üsulla icra edilib. Müasir dövrdə bu ərazidə quşların mozaik yayılmasını 2 qrupa ayırmaq olar: səciyyəvi və qeyri-səciyyəvi meşə quşları. Birinci qrupun həyat təzi meşədən tam asılıdır, amma 2-ci qrup meşədə nəsil verir, yemlənmək və başqa təlabatı üçün açıq sahələrə uçurlar.

Açar sözlər: Quş, fauna, say dinamikası, növ, areal

**Типичные И Нетипичные Репродуктивные Популяции Птиц
В Губинских И Алтыгачских Лесах**

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Восточно-кавказские леса и талышские леса являются отдельными зоогеографическими регионами. Сведения об авиофауне этих регионов имеются, начиная с 19 века и до нашего времени, но сравнительная информация по распределению птиц в этих лесах до сих пор не проводилась. Данные, приведенные в статье, были накоплены в 2013-2015 годах автором. Для оценки материала используется мультипараметрный анализ. Основной причиной современного мозаичного распределения птиц по данным территориям является влияние антропогенного фактора. В настоящее время птицы, населяющие данную территорию, могут быть разделены на две группы, в соответствии по типу использования леса. Типичные лесные и нетипичные лесные. Весь образ жизни первой группы связан с лесами. Вторая группа использует леса только для размножения, но они перелетают в открытые ландшафты для питания и других потребностей.

Ключевые слова: *Птицы, фауна, динамика численность, вид, ареал*